

Democratic Election Process: Transparency & Credibility

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DOI - 10.5281/zenodo.18955361

As per my study, USA is the mother of democracy. In 1776 thirteen colonies fought against the British Emperor. Thomas Jefferson is called as the father of the American constitution. Thereafter the people of France and the USSR made a revolution in their countries respectively. This revolution means the voice of common people against the monarchy. Prior to East India Company, we also had a number of Monarchs in our dispersed provinces. After independence we accepted democracy in which the electoral process is very important.

Objective:

The researcher has decided the following objectives on the given topic.

1. To study the electoral process in democratic country.
2. To verify the comments of oppositions on the electoral process.
3. To suggest the measures on it.

Definitions of the Democracy:

Abraham Lincoln said, " the democracy is the state of the people, for the people by the people"

Voultear propounded for the monarchy a lion's state is a very strong one instead of the state of hundreds of mice. In spite of this he stressed upon democracy and inspired the French.

Montesque propounded for the separation of power for democratic countries.

Our Indian constitution accepted the separation of power. The power is separated into the three pillars that are legislative, executive and judiciary.

Some constitutional institutions that are autonomous in our country. Prior to the independence we had a number of provinces on which a monarch's power was there. Some Gharanas ran their kingdom. The word of the King was final. He was the justice; he was the protector of religion; he had the powers to fight a battle. Such as Ghulam Gharana, Sultan Shahi, Moghal Gharana, The province of Satara; the province of Jhansi; province of Indoor; province of Gwalior; province of Hyderabad; province of Junagarh; province of Kashmir and etc. At the time of the independence we had 602 provinces with their Badshah. (Kings)

After the independence we the people of India constituted a constituent assembly for the constitution in which fundamental rights of the people and other constitutional institutes are mentioned, such as Central Vigilance Commission, Central Water commission, Union Public Service Commission, State Public Service Commission, Central Election Commission, etc. In a democratic country the Election Commission's role is vital.

The Powers of the Election Commission:

1. To make a schedule of the general elections.
2. To declare the programme to register the new voters' name.

3. To allot the election cards to the voters.
4. To omit the dead voters' name from the election register.
5. To announce the election programme with code of conduct.
6. To depute the returning officers in every district.
7. To depute the observer in the election process.
8. To give the training of the procedure of the election, etc.
9. To give status & recognition to the political parties either they are national or regional.
10. To conduct the elections in a free, fair and transparent manner.

In 1986, Electronic Voting Machines entered into the election process of India.

I have taken interviews of one hundred of the people from Nanded city in this regard. 67 % of the population tended that elections in our country should be based on ballot papers to increase the credibility and transparency of the democracy.

Such other things found that an independent candidate takes zero votes in his constituency. This does mean the candidate also did not vote for himself. Where is the credibility?

Among the Muslim population area a staunch Hindu candidate gets victory. Is it possible? Who brought EVM in our country is not important. Is any manipulation possible in that? It is very important. If suppose all of the oppositions are of the opinion to conduct the elections on ballot, their demand is also to be considered.

The present atmosphere of the world is a very dangerous one. Leaders are being elected in the name of democracy and functioning as a dictator while in power. The powerful countries attack neighbours and their sovereignty. Election in ballot papers is the concrete one. The election on electronic voting machines is an abstract one. EVM is also good but VVPAT slips should be counted on demand by any candidate. If not this, then ballot is better. The Election Commission should be neutral for the free and fair elections.

No matter of the mother of democracy and father of the constitution. The matter is that now the USA has the MOAB (mother of all bombs) and Russia has FOAB (father of all bombs). UNO is dishevelled. The world is going back towards autocracy. Good leadership can prevent this and save the world from the bombing culture.